

METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING READING CLASSES BASED ON MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: this article talks about interactive methods, innovative technologies, the use of pedagogical and information technologies, pedagogical technologies in the educational process. Interactive methods are discussed.

Keywords: study lessons, modern educational technologies, pedagogical technologies, pedagogical technologies, methods.

Today, the interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day, one of the reasons for this is that until now, traditional education If in lim, students are taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, modern technologies teach them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, to study and analyze independently, and even to draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance. In the process of education, the student becomes the main figure. Therefore, modern teaching methods, interactive methods, and innovative technologies play an important role in training qualified professionals in higher educational institutions and faculties. Knowledge, experience and interactive methods of pedagogic technology and pedagogic skills ensure that students acquire knowledgeable, mature skills. Innovation (English innavation) is innovation, innovation. Innovative technologies are the introduction of innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers and students, and in its implementation mainly interactive methods are fully used.

Interactive methods are called collective thinking, that is, they are methods of pedagogical influence and are a component of educational content. The uniqueness of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of pedagogues and students. Such a process of pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, which include the following: - forcing the student not to be indifferent during the lesson, to think independently, to create and search;

- Ensuring that pupils-students are constantly interested in knowledge during the educational process;

-Increasing the student's interest in knowledge independently with a creative approach to each issue;

-Organization of activities of pedagogue and student-student in cooperation.

In the opinion of teachers, researchers, and practitioners studying the issues and problems of pedagogical technologies, pedagogical technology is related only to information technology, and it is necessary to use a computer, distance learning or various is defined as

the use of different techniques. In our opinion, the main basis of the pedagogical technology depends on the technologies selected for the cooperation of the teacher and the student-student to achieve a guaranteed result from the specified goal, that is, used in the process of teaching to achieve a guaranteed result according to the goal each educational technology can organize cooperative activities between the teacher and the student, both can achieve positive results, if the students can think independently, work positively, search, analyze during the learning process if they can, if they can make their own conclusions, if they can evaluate themselves, the group, and the group can evaluate them, and the teacher can create opportunities and conditions for such activities, in our opinion, this is the basis of the teaching process. Each lesson, topic, educational subject has its own technology, that is, pedagogical technology in the educational process is an individual process, which is directed to a goal based on the needs of the student is a pedagogical process aimed at providing a planned and guaranteed result.

The model of the link, which is thought out in every detail, is the design, organization and conduct of the educational process with the unconditional provision of comfortable conditions for students and teachers, or meaningful technique of implementing the educational process.

Learning is carried out in such a way that the assimilation of knowledge is carried out not only on the basis of memorization, but also through the conscious application of knowledge in the process of solving cognitive tasks. In this, students learn to reason and use the available information.

In the process of organizing training sessions, the following are used: problem questions, programmed tasks, tasks differentiated by cards at the stage of knowledge verification and consolidation, didactic games. All these didactic materials provide various types of support (organization, stimulation, training) in the process of formation of mental operations. Thus, we can conclude that teaching usually requires not one, but several methods, their complex. Different teaching methods increase students' knowledge activity. The combination of methods allows to take into account the specific features of the content of the educational material in the best way, to choose the most reasonable methods of acquiring knowledge. Based on the use of active educational technologies, conditions are created for the comprehensive development of the student's cognitive abilities.

Modern technologies used in teaching and upbringing:

1. Corrective and developmental educational technologies.
2. Game technologies.
3. Differential education technologies.
4. Technologies of collective education.
5. Technology of individualization of education.
6. Project teaching technologies.
7. Problematic educational technologies.
8. Health-saving technologies.
9. Person-oriented technologies.
10. Information and communication technologies.

Corrective development-acquisition technologies. These technologies allow the most flexible response to the educational needs and opportunities of each child. The concept of "game technology" includes a wide enough group of methods and methods of organizing the

pedagogical process in the form of various educational games. In general, unlike games, a pedagogical game has an important feature - it is characterized by a clearly defined goal of teaching and a corresponding pedagogical result, its justification, identification in a clear form, and a cognitive orientation. The game form of the lessons is created with the motivation of the game, which serves as a means of motivating and encouraging students to study.

Differential educational technologies. A differentiated (multi-level) approach to teaching is seen as an opportunity to individualize teaching in a small group / group. The differential approach is one of the components of the psychological comfort of students, because it includes, if possible, the elimination of all stress-generating factors of the educational process, creating an atmosphere in the classroom that relaxes children.

Collective learning technologies. Using the method of collective organization of educational activities increases the effectiveness of corrective and developmental education.

Project technologies. The project method is not new in world pedagogy. It was proposed and developed by the American philosopher and educator George Dewey in the 1920s, and is based on it. In the field of humanistic ideas of philosophy and education, J. Dewey proposed to build learning on an active basis. Purposeful activity: taking into account the personal interest of students in this knowledge and, as a result, achieving a real result.

Problematic educational technologies. The problem of organizing training using active methods has attracted the attention of many researchers, because this knowledge and skills are formed most effectively in the process of problem-based learning. The use of elements of problem-based education helps to increase the level of scientific education, to develop students' independence, thinking and creative abilities, emotional and volitional qualities, and to form students' cognitive motivation to learn.

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